

Electrical and Mechanical Properties of Polypyrrole-Cellulose Fiber Composites Synthesized Via a Novel Chemical Processing Route

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SUMMARY

The polymerization of pyrrole onto a cellulose fiber has been carried out using the ionic liquid (IL), 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate. The results show promise for an efficient and convenient route to the preparation of conductive cellulose fiber composites coated with the conductive polymer polypyrrole. It was observed that both resistance and strength of polypyrrole/cellulose fiber composites decrease with increased monomer concentration. An optimum oxidant absorption time and temperature were estimated from the experiments.

Keywords: cotton thread; conductive cellulose; polypyrrole; ionic liquid; tensile strength

INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, the use of intrinsic conducting polymers (ICPs) has attracted considerable inquiry because of their immense variety of physical and electronic/conductive properties. These conducting polymers have been prominent in applications ranging from organic transistors [1] and coatings for fuel cells [2] to functional textiles [3], and electromagnetic shielding [4]. Among the many electrically conductive polymers that have been given attention to over the last decade, polypyrrole (PPy), which consists of five membered heterocyclic rings, has become especially important because of its low resistivity, redox properties, and environmental stability. However, the formation of these conductive polymers into nanostructures has proved to be difficult. Previous studies have achieved conductive polymerization on fibers such as wool [5], cotton [6], and nylon [7] through the use of electrochemical and chemical oxidation, and in rare cases, vapor phase polymerization [8]. Though these processes have achieved certain electrical properties, it has been with the consequence of significant degradation in mechanical properties [6].

We have taken a new approach by using a novel solvent, Ionic Liquids (ILs; defined as salts that melt below 100 °C), to incorporate nanosized conducting polymers onto cellulose to enhance both mechanical and conductive properties. ILs can dissolve cellulose [9], as well as serve as a solvent to polymerize pyrrole [10]. By combining

these two properties into a single IL we envisioned an IL that will not only effectively impregnate cellulose fibers, but also efficiently polymerize pyrrole resulting in electrically conductive cellulose fiber composites. Here we report our initial results.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials & Chemicals

Commercially available 100% cotton thread (Gütermann - CA 02776) and 100% viscose thread (Sulky - CA 45688) were purchased locally. Pyrrole monomer and iron(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were obtained from Aldrich (Milwaukee, WI). 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ([Emim]Cl) was provided by BASF Corporation (Ludwigshafen, Germany). Concentrated sulfuric acid was obtained from Fisher Scientific (Fair Lawn, NJ). All chemicals and materials were used as received. Deionized water was used throughout and obtained from a commercial in-house deionizer.

Synthesis of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate, [Emim][FeCl₄]

Synthesis of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate (Fig. 1) was carried out similar to previously reported methods for 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate [11]. Briefly, the iron(III) chloride hexahydrate and [Emim]Cl were weighed out in stoichiometric ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 1:2 mole ratio and placed in a beaker. The beaker was then put in an oven at 90 °C for 30 min after which near quantitative exclusion of water from the IL-metal chloride salt was observed. The [Emim][FeCl₄] solution was poured into a separatory funnel for ease of separation of the 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate bottom phase. The water-rich top phase was discarded.

Figure 1. Structure of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate, [Emim][FeCl₄].

Absorption of [Emim][FeCl₄] into fiber

The Gütermann's pure cotton thread or Sulky's viscose thread were weighed prior to [Emim][FeCl₄] impregnation. For adequate immersion, slits were made in straws of ca. 4 mm o.d. using a razor. One slit was cut at the top of the straw in a vertical direction, while the other was sliced about 2.5-3 cm from the top of the straw in the horizontal direction. These slits facilitated in holding the fiber surrounding the straw. A 15.24 cm cotton fiber was fitted in the slits and loosely wrapped in the 2.5 -3 cm length of the straw.

3 mL of [Emim][FeCl₄] was added to several test tubes after which the straws with fibers were placed inside. A test tube rack containing the test tubes with straws were placed in a New Brunswick Scientific C25 Incubator Shaker (Edison, NJ) which was preset at 22 °C and shaken at 100 rpm. Cellulose fibers were removed at time intervals of 1, 5, 10, 15, and 30 min. Further studies were also conducted for the Gütermann cellulose fiber in which the temperature was adjusted to 30, 40, or 50 °C by the shaker,

as well as using ILs prepared with 1:2 and 2:1 molar ratios of [Emim]Cl and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Multiple Fiber Absorption of [Emim][FeCl₄]

In addition to single Fe(III) absorption studies, a multiple use fiber study was performed. 5 mL of IL was transferred to a test tube. Gütermann fibers of 30.48 cm were placed on a straw length of 4 cm. The straw was placed in the IL solution for 1 h. The weight was recorded. The second straw was then placed in the same IL solution for another hour. The weight was recorded. The same process was followed for a 10 multiple fiber study to observe the maximum amount of iron(III) that could be absorbed from the solution.

Atomic Absorption Analysis of Iron(III)

Samples were prepared for atomic absorption testing using a PerkinElmer A400 Analyst Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). The entire fiber samples were weighed and then tightly packed at the bottom of test tubes. Samples were then treated with 1 mL of sulfuric acid. The cellulose fiber impregnated with [Emim][FeCl₄] dissolved into solution. Next, this solution was diluted to 50 mL with deionized water. Samples were quantitatively analyzed for Fe(III) by AAS using a standard calibration curve. Blanks and controls were prepared using cellulose fibers.

Pyrrole Polymerization

Pyrrole polymerization was carried out on fibers immersed for 15 min at 22 °C in 1:1 molar ratio [Emim][FeCl₄]. These constraints were used for efficiency but moreover, for the reason that iron absorption seemed to be highest at 15 min.

After 15 min of absorption for the 15.24 cm fibers, they were removed and remained wrapped on the straws. The fibers were patted dry using a paper towel so no iron chloride or IL residue remained on the fibers. Then, fibers were placed in pyrrole solutions of various concentrations for 24 h. The different solutions of pyrrole and water used were 0.1% and 5% pyrrole. After soaking in pyrrole solution, the straw intact fibers were removed and soaked in distilled water for 3 min so any excess polypyrrole (Fig. 2) on the surface was removed. Fibers were finally removed from the straw and then dried.

Figure 2. Polypyrrole structure.

TEM Optical Imaging

Transmission Electron Microscopy was performed on both treated and untreated Gütermann cotton fibers. Desiccated samples were embedded in Spurr's low viscosity resin for 8 h under vacuum then polymerized overnight at 70 °C. Blocks were trimmed and 92_ nm thick sections cut on Leica EM UC6 Ultramicrotome using a diamond knife. Samples were placed on 0.5% Formvar coated slot grids and visualized on a Hitachi H-7650 TEM using 60 kV of acceleration voltage. Photographs were obtained using an AMT Digital Camera.

Electrical Resistance Measurement

Resistance was recorded using a Fluke 112 (Everett, WA) multimeter. One end was placed in the beginning of the fiber and the other 1 cm away. The resistance was then recorded.

Mechanical Properties

The strength, modulus, and failure strain data were determined from the stress strain plot using an electrical motor driven MTS Q-Test 25 testing machine. A special pneumatic clamping device was used for clamping the specimens and a load cell of 5 lbs was used in the testing machine. The test was carried out at a crosshead speed of 0.127 cm/min. The gauge length of the fiber was maintained at 7.62 cm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the above process, oxidant absorption was optimized by using different oxidant concentrations, absorption times, and absorption temperatures to achieve a low surface resistivity onto cellulose fibers. Using our IL process, hazardous chemical residue and heat formation were removed. Though the investigation shows a degradation of cellulose fibers, the ongoing efforts on the assembly of nanostructured materials is expected to cause an increase in mechanical and electrical properties of polypyrrole/cellulose composites. The preliminary results provided below shows promise of an efficient and convenient route to the preparation of conductive polypyrrole/cellulose fiber composites.

Absorption of Iron(III) ions on Cellulose Fibers: *Effects of Fibers*

When absorption was measured as a function of time (Fig. 3), absorption seemed to have a relative peak around 10 min with Fe(III) absorption of 65 mg/g. This value is a significant improvement in time needed and Fe(III) absorbed over aqueous FeCl₃ conditioning described by Beneventi *et al.* [6]. Absorption of Fe(III) appears to peak then decline after 10 min for the Gütermann cotton thread. Obviously, Fe(III) absorption into the cotton and viscose thread does not follow a simple uptake process over time, and this requires further study to fully understand this complicated process. Accuracy was measured as the average of at least three measurements. Error bars were not plotted due to the limited number of measurements in some cases. Fifteen min conditioning times for [Emim][FeCl₄] for cotton and viscose are recommended.

Figure 3. Fe (III) absorption of cotton thread (solid line) and viscose thread (dotted line) versus time at 22 °C.

Absorption of Iron(III) ions on Cotton Fibers: *Effects of Molar Ratio*

The molar ratio also had an effect on the Fe(III) absorption to the cotton thread. As seen in Fig. 4, as the ratio between iron chloride and IL was increased, the amount of Fe(III) absorbed also increased. The results clearly indicate that the molar ratio of [Emim]Cl and FeCl₃•6H₂O used to prepare the [Emim][FeCl₄] IL leads to variable concentrations of Fe(III) available for subsequent reaction with pyrrole monomer. While the 1:2 molar ratio IL would seem best suited for pyrrole polymerization, investigation of pyrrole polymerization using 1:1 molar ratio IL was also studied further.

Figure 4. Fe(III) absorption of cotton thread from differing molar ratio of [Emim]Cl and FeCl₃•6H₂O at 22 °C and 15 min

Absorption of Iron(III) ions on Cotton Fibers: *Effects of Multiple [Emim][FeCl₄] Usage*

A series of ten Gütermann cotton fibers were conditioned using the same [Emim][FeCl₄] solution at 22 °C and 1 h (data not shown). The amount of Fe(III) absorbed showed no significant decrease for the first three cotton fibers conditioned. The fourth cotton fiber conditioned in the same [Emim][FeCl₄] resulted in a 23% decrease in the amount of absorbed Fe(III). Absorption of Fe(III) steadily decreased over the remaining cotton threads conditioned with the 10th cotton thread resulting in a 60% decrease in Fe(III) absorption. This study suggests a maximum capacity of Fe(III) absorption is possible for three conditioning cycles; however, Fe(III) seems to have been depleted from the IL for the later cycles.

Absorption of Iron(III) ions on Cotton Fibers: *Effects of Temperature*

Temperature has an effect on Fe(III) absorption. Fig. 5 plots the Fe(III) absorption versus temperature for cotton threads conditioned in [Emim][FeCl₄] for 15 min. It was observed that as temperature increased, the Fe(III) absorption increased as one would expect. Increases in temperature resulted in an increase in absorption primarily through increased diffusion mass transfer of the [Emim][FeCl₄] into the cotton thread.

Figure 5. Fe(III) absorption of cotton thread vs temperature and 15 min conditioning.

TEM of Polypyrrole-coated Cotton Fibers

The cross-sectional views of untreated and polypyrrole-coated Gütermann cotton thread are shown in Fig. 6. Figures 6a and 6b are indicative of commercially available mercerized cotton fibers [12]. The cross sections have irregular sizes and there appears to be dark regions or patches that resemble cliffs or valleys which we believe are caused by wrinkling during TEM sample preparation. These regions are present within all samples imaged here.

Polypyrrole nano particles appear as black flecks on the surface and within the cotton fiber (Fig. 6c and 6d). The formation of these nanosized polypyrrole particles and controlled dispersion may assist in improving mechanical properties of polypyrrole-cellulose fiber composites. Cross sections of the polypyrrole-coated cotton fibers (Fig. 6c and 6d) shows greater accumulation of nanoscale structures of polypyrrole at the edges with varying sizes of nanoparticles within the interior of the fiber. One can see in Fig. 6d that ~90% of the polypyrrole nanoscale structures are on the edge of the cotton fiber.

Figure 6. TEM images of Gütermann cotton thread: without polypyrrole at a) 3000x and b) 50,000x magnification and with polypyrrole at c) 3000x and d) 50,000x magnification.

Electrical Properties of Polypyrrole-coated Cotton Fibers

Resistance values at 1 cm for PPy-coated cotton fibers showed a marked decrease as the pyrrole monomer concentration was increased (see Table 1). Increasing pyrrole monomer resulted in thicker PPy coating as evidenced by the black covering of PPy on the cotton fibers. The PPy-coated cotton thread prepared from 0.1% pyrrole had a grey color indicating regions on the cotton thread having less PPy coating, whereas the PPy-coated cotton thread prepared using 5% pyrrole was completely black.

Table 1. Resistance of the PPy/cotton threads*

Pyrrole Concentration	0.1%	5%
Resistance (k Ω) @ 1 cm	1518	2.99

*Experimental conditions: fibers immersed for 15 min at 22 °C in 1:1 molar ratio [Emim][FeCl₄], polymerization time = 24 h.

Mechanical Properties of Polypyrrole-coated Cotton Fibers

The stress-strain plots for cotton thread prepared with differing amounts of pyrrole in solution are shown in Fig. 7 and the corresponding data are provided in Table 2. The data clearly show a decrease in ultimate stress and increase in failure strain for the polypyrrole-coated cotton thread in comparison to untreated cotton thread. The elastic moduli of polypyrrole-coated cotton threads are also less than that for the untreated cotton thread. The general results of this study show that increasing incorporation of polypyrrole on cotton thread results in a degradation of mechanical properties; however this degradation in mechanical properties is relatively small.

Figure 7. Stress-strain curves for Gütermann cotton thread treated with pyrrole solutions of 0% (solid line), 0.1% (dotted line), and 5% (dashed line).

Table 2. Tensile Strength Studies of PPy/cotton thread*

Pyrrole Concentration	0 %	0.1 %	5 %
Modulus (MPa)	271.31	230.46	239.82
Ultimate Stress (MPa)	36.60	30.13	33.46
Failure Strain (%)	13.06	13.00	14.0

* Experimental conditions: fibers immersed for 15 minutes at 22 °C in 1:1 molar ratio Emim[FeCl₄], polymerization time = 24 hours.

CONCLUSION

A novel process has been developed to fabricate nanostructured conductive polypyrrole-cellulose fiber composites using IL solvent. The Fe(III) absorption shows a peak value 65 mg/g around 10 min which indicates a significant improvement in comparison to other processing routes. An increased absorption of Fe(III) is observed as the molar

ratio between IL and iron chloride is decreased. The Fe(III) absorption is also seen to be higher at elevated temperature (55 °C) compared to room temperature. TEM observation shows increased amounts of nanostructured polypyrrole particles near the edges of the cotton fibers. The resistance of the conductive cellulose fiber composite is reduced significantly with increased amount of pyrrole concentration. A partial degradation of strength and stiffness and increased failure strain are observed in the conductive cellulose fibers. Further studies are underway to examine a protonated bath opposed to an unprotonated bath.

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